

Digital Marketing in the Indian Situation

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E.Kaviya & P.Anupriya

*S.D.N.B Vaishnav College for Women
(M.com Accounting & Finance)*

Abstract

Internet marketing is rising in India at the fast pace. Many Indian companies are using internet marketing for competitive advantages. The success of a marketing campaign cannot entirely be achieved by internet marketing only. Moderately for the success of only marketing campaign, it should fully strap the capabilities of various marketing techniques available within both traditional and modern marketing. Startups that use internet marketing many times get neglected.

This study shows protection to be taken for effective execution of internet marketing to harvest enormous potential to accession the sales.

Keywords: Internet marketing, Social network, Neglected, Online retail, accession.

Introduction

Internet Marketing is any form of marketing products or services, which involves electronic devices. It can be both online and offline. According to CAM Foundation, -"Online marketing is a set of tools and methodologies used for promoting and services through the internet."

The internet marketing hue cycle fluctuates under dodge preconditions. This internet marketing connects organizations with qualified potential customers and takes business development to a much higher level than conventional marketing. Online marketing fuse the internet ingenious and technical tools, including pattern, expansion, sale, and advertising, while concentrating on the primary business design such as E-Commerce, Lead-based websites, Affiliate marketing, and Local Search. In internet marketing, harem audience is reachable at a bridge of traditional advertising budgets, allowing the business to create appealing consumes ads. Consumers will research and purchase products and service at the license as the internet market is flexible and convenient. Here consumers can be demographically targeted much more adequately in an online rather than an offline process. The main online plat form used here is Google, Face book, Twitter, YouTube, etc., in recent Instagram is also popular are they are undulating out more advertises friendly products that are beguiling smalls as well as large players to market with high efficiency to early adopters. The advertises investment depends on how fast the emerging digital content industry endorses scientific measurement tool. Mostly brand is an experiment to a large extent with expressing themselves through online and youth content.

Interesting Facts about Internet Marketing

These days’ people spend more time on the internet than on the service. The liability is quite wide on the internet as correlated to other media of marketing. The various forms of internet marketing such as sites, social media, etc., make it a lot easier for the players to convey with people. Customers get to know about each new product in the market instantaneously. Thus it fascinates more attention of people.

The marketing scenario enables to share advertisement campaign together on different plat forms. Millions of customers are handled simultaneously. The way the tasks are less time consuming and exhausting. Internet marketing does not need much capital investment. All it needs is some good site writing skill.

Internet marketing is available on 24/7 basis. Which means internet marketing doesn’t work based on the schedule. It is available on the net from the moment you upload it on internet. In internet marketing, everything is available just one click away. Whether its fashion or home appliances or gadgets, etc., select your choice and go on. Internet marketing gave a track to internet banking to enter into the digital world. Which made payment methods digital. The ensures quick and instant payment services over the net. The services start one the ads are raise online. Even after the products sold, the campaign remains which attract more use demand. There is no time limit for how long the service can last in Internet marketing. It provides long lasting and continues to affect on the customers and attracts them by its way.

Reasons for rising in Internet Marketing in India

Internet penetration will increase around 900 million Indians by 2022. Latest trends in internet marketing in India in web usage, mobile and search, social networking, shopping, and online video are shaping the Indian internet marketplace and what it holds for the years to come.

Fig 1 India is now world second largest internet population

By adding 627 million users in 2018 and exhibiting a year-over-year increase of 47.54 % India becomes to be the world second-largest internet population leaving behind China. While in 2017, Mobile Internet grew 5 billion users during 2018 the growth was 63 percent. India registered a YoYo of 28 percent in 2018 and a YoY growth of 39 percent in 2018 as far as the number of internet users is concerned.

Fig 2 Maximum of Social media users

- 86% of Social Media users in India.
- 217 minutes are spent on Face book by minimum user.
- Face book audience are increase 28% in the last year.
- 59,642,000 users visited Face book on their laptops.
- Pinterest and Instagram are the fastest growing networks.

Fig 3 Entertainment and online video continues to grow

- 74% of entertainment site visitors in India.
- 31.5 million Viewers watched YouTube videos in India.
- 27% increase in the India online video Audience over a year.
- 54,025,000 people watched an online video on their laptops.

Indian Government promotes Digital India

From 69 million online shoppers in 2018 and more than 100 million in 2019, India has seen a stark rise in the internet population. Ever since the launch of Digital India in 2015 as an initiative to improve online infrastructure and digital empowerment, there has been mushrooming of a whole market of start-ups, services, and more than connect people globally! It has resulted in a rise of active internet users, mobile connections, social media traffic, and more.

Commandments of Internet Marketing

Digital method is created in a complete void from the overall brand strategy, or worse, no digital strategy is crafted at all. Since digital is the glue that ties the entirety of a marketing plan and campaign together, anything that happens online needs to ladder up to the higher objectives of the brand. An effective digital strategy is typically composed of a group of sub-strategies to effectively plan and accounts for owned, earned, shared, and paid assets.

Majority of brands have some sort of goal around innovation. And that's important because creation drive the business forward, But innovation means better, not new. Your strategy should help you select your campaign, not the other way around. If you're seeking to use a tool or platform as a result of you think that it's innovative, and can't identify how or why it works for your audience, you're worshipping the shiny object and area unit destined to fail.

Conclusion

Internet marketing has increased in last few years in India. People have different views about it. But the fact is this Internet marketing has amazing probable to increase in sales provided businesses should have the knowledge to implement it in the right way. Benefits like increased brand appreciation and better brand reliability can be gained by effective Internet media plan. Internet marketing campaign help in reduction in costs, boost in inbound traffic, and better ranking in search engines.

References

1. TS, Anoop (Dec. 01, 2014). Digital marketing communication "mix." [www.linkedin.com/20141201185400-100431809-digital mark.](http://www.linkedin.com/20141201185400-100431809-digital-mark)
2. Murthy, Srinivas (Jan. 06, 2016). Always keep your customers close and your loyalist closer. [articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com > collections > digital marketing.](http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/collections/digital-marketing)
3. Making digital and traditional marketing work together, Econsultancy Apr 2013 MatthewKates, Matthew (17 April 2013).
4. Digital marketing is growing in Australia, but so is the skills gap, E-consultancy, archived from the original on 21Oct 2012 Claire Brinkley, Claire (18 October 2012).
5. Worldwide Ad Growth Buoyed by Digital, Mobile Adoption, e-Marketer, archived from the original on (12Sep 2013).
6. E merchandiser (25 September 2013), Worldwide Ad Growth Buoyed by Digital, Mobile Adoption, e-Marketer, archived from the initial on (12 Gregorian calendar month 2013).